

Green synthesis of copper nanoparticles using *Daucus carota* leaf extract and their anticancer activity against Hep3B liver cancer cells

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Abstract

Background: Hepatocellular carcinoma is among the most prevalent forms of cancer globally, and its treatment is often hindered by drug resistance and systemic toxicity. Recent advances in nanomedicine have enabled the development of metal-based nanoparticles with improved targeting efficiency and reduced side effects. In this context, green synthesis using medicinal plants presents a sustainable and biocompatible alternative for nanoparticle fabrication.

Methods: Copper nanoparticles (CuNPs) were synthesized using an aqueous extract derived from *Daucus carota* leaves through a phytochemical-assisted reduction method. A 4 mM copper nitrate solution was reacted with 10 mL of concentrated leaf extract under constant stirring at 60 °C for 4 hours. The resulting nanoparticles were characterized using UV–Vis spectroscopy, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), and FTIR analysis. Anti-proliferative activity was assessed via MTT assay on Hep3B liver carcinoma cells across a concentration gradient (10–100 µg/mL).

Results: The synthesized CuNPs exhibited an average particle diameter of 58.3 nm with an irregular-spherical morphology, as revealed by TEM. UV–Vis spectroscopy confirmed a strong surface plasmon resonance peak at 276 nm. XRD patterns suggested a polycrystalline structure, and FTIR spectra indicated the presence of phenolic and carboxylic groups from the plant extract on the nanoparticle surface. In vitro cytotoxicity studies demonstrated a dose-dependent inhibition of Hep3B cells, with an estimated IC₅₀ value of 62 µg/mL for CuNPs, compared to 7.8 µg/mL for the reference chemotherapeutic agent, 5-fluorouracil.

Conclusion: Biologically synthesized copper nanoparticles using *Daucus carota* extract exhibit promising anticancer potential against hepatic tumor cells. The eco-friendly synthetic route and moderate cytotoxicity profile support further investigation into their application in targeted cancer therapy.

Keywords

carcinoma, hepatocellular, *Daucus carota*, copper (II) nitrate

Introduction

Cancer is one of the leading causes of mortality, with liver cancer among the top ten, leading to approximately 1 million deaths annually (Hussain and Lafta 2021). Currently, conventional cancer treatments include chemotherapy and radiotherapy; however, these treatments cause toxic side effects to normal cells (Mula-Hussain et al. 2021; Adebayo et al. 2024). As a solution to this problem, the use of nanoparticle-based systems was proposed, which can be employed for diagnostics and/or imaging and to deliver drugs, radiosensitizers, or other therapeutic agents specifically to tumors, thus improving therapeutic efficacy and reducing side effects. Silver, gold, silica, and iron oxide nanoparticles, for example, have been shown to boost tumor therapy (Sih et al. 2025; Tabbasam et al. 2025). Nanoparticles can also be synthesized using a greener method—applying ecological principles and natural resources (Hussein and Al-Saffar 2025). The biosynthesis method offers multiple advantages, such as mild reaction conditions, a production process that is easily controlled, and the potential integration into hybrid nanoformulations with drugs (Abdelhamid et al. 2025; Paul et al. 2025). Biosynthesis routes to metal-based nanoparticles are mainly based on the deposition of ions through microbial, plant extract, or metabolite treatments (Adeyemi et al. 2022; Wahab et al. 2023; Dheyab et al. 2024). Highly concentrated amounts of metal ions are present in mining and metallurgical effluents, creating serious environmental issues. If the microorganisms or plants used to enhance the nanoparticle synthesis processes are further applied to the removal of metal ions from aqueous media, the two steps can be efficiently combined. Interestingly, copper nanoparticles have been shown to exhibit antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral activities. Nanoparticles can therefore be used as therapeutic agents to treat tumors and for tumor diagnostics by imaging or for photothermal therapy (Al-Snafi et al. 2022; Shalabi et al. 2024).

Different physicochemical techniques have been used for NP synthesis, including chemical vapor deposition, sputtering techniques, electrochemical processing, laser ablation, photoreduction, and chemical reduction in solution (Mahmood et al. 2023). However, these techniques are expensive, time-consuming, and require extreme conditions. Biological methods represent alternative strategies for obtaining NPs, since they are low-cost, environmentally friendly, and reliable and do not require extreme reaction conditions (Mohammed et al. 2020; Adwan and AL-Rekabi 2025). These processes can include plants and plant extracts, fungi, yeasts, and bacteria (Falih et al. 2023). The advantages of biological NP synthesis include the use of living organisms, higher production rates, and less toxic byproducts (Pandit et al. 2022).

Copper nanoparticles (CuNPs) are metallic copper particles with diameters on the nanoscale (Crisan et al. 2021; Yang et al. 2024).

Daucus carota: medicinal properties and uses

The carrot, native to Central Asia, is a biennial flowering plant in the family Apiaceae. In addition to the edible taproot, the plant also produces toxic alkaloids. In folk medicine, the roots and seeds are used for the treatment of many disorders, including gastrointestinal problems, skin diseases, gout, rheumatism, diabetes, and urolithiasis (Dehghani et al. 2025). Carrots are rich in antioxidants, polyacetylenes, and carotenoids, including beta-carotene, lutein, and zeaxanthin. They are also a rich source of vitamins C and K, as well as vitamin B6 and the minerals potassium, manganese, and magnesium (Mohammed 2016). They contain beta-carotene, fiber, potassium, and vitamin K and may provide other essential nutrients such as calcium and magnesium. The root contains a large amount of fiber and carotene (Ismail et al. 2023).

Traditional medicine recommends carrots as a medicinal plant for kidney disease, bladder infections, dental disease, digestive disorders, and other issues (Mustafa et al. 2024a). The anti-inflammatory activity of carrot roots has been attributed to their rich content of carotenoids, particularly zeta-carotene (Christopher et al. 2024). Accordingly, the present study aimed to biosynthesize copper nanoparticles using *Daucus carota* leaf extract through a green chemistry approach, followed by comprehensive physicochemical characterization and evaluation of their anticancer potential against hepatic carcinoma cells (Mohammed et al. 2021; Mahdi and Shakir 2025).

Materials and methods

Collection and authentication of plant material

Fresh leaves of *Daucus carota* L. (wild carrot) were collected during the early spring season (September 2024) from several parts of Iraq. Only healthy, mature leaves were selected for the extraction process (Selvakumar and Kalia 2024).

Preparation of plant extract

The collected leaves were thoroughly rinsed with tap water, followed by distilled water, to remove surface contaminants and soil particles (Al-Safadi 2008). The cleaned leaves were air-dried in the shade at room temperature (28 ± 2 °C) for 7 days to prevent the degradation of heat-sensitive phytoconstituents (Selvakumar and Kalia 2025). Dried leaves were pulverized using a laboratory-scale electric grinder and stored in airtight amber glass containers in a cool, dry place until further use (Ogidi et al. 2024).

To obtain the aqueous extract, 20 g of powdered leaf material was mixed with 200 mL of deionized water and heated at 70 °C for 1 hour under continuous magnetic stirring (Shebaby et al. 2015). The mixture was allowed

to cool, then filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper, followed by centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes to remove particulate matter. The supernatant was collected and stored at 4 °C as the stock plant extract for nanoparticle synthesis (Rana et al. 2025).

Green synthesis of copper nanoparticles

Copper nanoparticles (CuNPs) were synthesized using the bioreduction potential of the phytoconstituents present in the *Daucus carota* extract. A 4 mM copper nitrate trihydrate ($\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) solution was prepared by dissolving 0.483 g in 500 mL of deionized water. The synthesis reaction was initiated by adding 25 mL of the prepared plant extract dropwise to 100 mL of the copper nitrate solution, stirred constantly at 60 °C. The reaction was maintained for 3 hours in a dark environment to avoid photoactivation.

A gradual color change from pale blue to dark green was visually observed, indicating the formation of CuNPs. The resulting colloidal suspension was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature, followed by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 20 minutes. The obtained pellet containing the copper nanoparticles was washed three times with ethanol and distilled water to eliminate any residual plant compounds or unreacted ions. The final pellet was dried in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 24 hours and stored in desiccators for further characterization.

The synthesis of copper nanoparticles was achieved through a green chemistry approach using *Daucus carota* leaf extract as a reducing and stabilizing agent. Upon gradual mixing of the aqueous plant extract with the copper nitrate precursor solution, a series of observable changes in the reaction mixture confirmed the formation of copper nanoparticles. Initially, the pale blue color of the copper salt solution began to shift toward a dark greenish-brown hue within the first 30 minutes of stirring. This visual transition indicated the reduction of Cu^{2+} ions to metallic Cu^0 nanoparticles mediated by the phytochemicals present in the extract, such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and other antioxidants. The color change is attributed to the excitation of surface plasmon vibrations, a hallmark of nanoparticle formation. To ensure controlled particle growth and uniform size distribution, the reaction was maintained at 60 °C under continuous stirring for 3 hours. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to near-neutral (approximately pH 7) using dilute sodium hydroxide (1 N NaOH), as a neutral to slightly alkaline environment favors reduction efficiency and particle stability in green synthesis protocols. After completion of the reaction, the suspension was allowed to cool to room temperature. The copper nanoparticles were then isolated by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 20 minutes, followed by sequential washing with ethanol and deionized water to remove unreacted biomolecules and residual ions. The washed pellet was oven-dried at 50 °C overnight, yielding a fine, dark green to brownish powder that was stored in air-

tight containers under desiccated conditions. The entire synthesis process was environmentally benign, free of toxic solvents or surfactants, and required no high-energy inputs, aligning with the principles of green nanotechnology. The obtained nanoparticles were subjected to further structural and functional characterization to confirm their morphology, crystallinity, and anticancer potential (Antonio-Pérez et al. 2023).

Characterization of copper nanoparticles

UV-visible spectroscopy

To confirm nanoparticle formation and monitor surface plasmon resonance (SPR), UV-Vis spectroscopy was performed using a JASCO V-730 spectrophotometer. The CuNP suspension was scanned in the range of 200–800 nm, and spectra were recorded at room temperature. The characteristic SPR absorption peak of copper nanoparticles was expected between 260 nm and 300 nm, indicating successful reduction of Cu^{2+} ions (Li et al. 2023).

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The morphology, shape, and size distribution of CuNPs were examined using a JEOL JEM-2100 transmission electron microscope operated at 200 kV. A small amount of CuNP powder was dispersed in ethanol, sonicated for 15 minutes, and placed onto carbon-coated copper grids. After air-drying, the grids were mounted for imaging. TEM images were analyzed using ImageJ software to determine the average particle size and distribution (Kirubakaran et al. 2024).

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis

To determine the crystallographic structure of the synthesized CuNPs, X-ray diffraction was performed using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$), operating at 40 kV and 30 mA. Samples were scanned over a 2θ range of 20°–80° at a scanning rate of 2°/min. The crystallite size was calculated using Scherrer's formula:

$$\frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} = D$$

where D is the average crystallite size, K is the shape factor (0.89), λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM), and θ is the Bragg angle.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR analysis was carried out using a Shimadzu IRTracer-100 spectrometer in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} to identify the functional groups responsible for the reduction and capping of CuNPs. Dried CuNPs were mixed with potassium bromide (KBr) and compressed into pellets before analysis. The absorption peaks were interpreted to detect biomolecules (such as flavonoids, phenolics, and proteins) involved in nanoparticle synthesis.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and zeta potential

To determine hydrodynamic size distribution and surface charge stability, DLS and zeta potential measurements were performed using a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS90. CuNPs were dispersed in deionized water, sonicated briefly, and analyzed at 25 °C. A zeta potential magnitude above ± 30 mV was considered indicative of high colloidal stability.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

The phytochemical profile of the *Daucus carota* extract used in CuNP synthesis was analyzed using a GC-MS system (Agilent 7890B GC system coupled with a 5977A MSD). The column used was HP-5MS (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m). The temperature program was set as follows: initial temperature at 60 °C (held for 2 min), ramped at 10 °C/min to 280 °C, held for 10 min. Injector temperature was maintained at 250 °C with helium as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Identification of compounds was performed using the NIST library database (Dawra et al. 2024).

In vitro cytotoxicity assay

Cell line and culture conditions

The human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line Hep3B was obtained from the Cell Bank of the Iraqi Center for Cancer Research. Cells were grown in DMEM (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 IU/mL penicillin, and 100 μ g/mL streptomycin.

MTT assay protocol

Cell viability was assessed using the standard MTT method. Briefly, Hep3B cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 5×10^3 cells per well and incubated overnight for adherence. Cells were treated with increasing concentrations (10, 25, 50, 75, and 100 μ g/mL) of CuNPs or *Daucus carota* extract dissolved in PBS. After 48 hours of treatment, 20 μ L of MTT solution (5 mg/mL in PBS) was added to each well and incubated for an additional 4 hours.

Following incubation, the medium was carefully aspirated, and the resulting formazan crystals were dissolved in 150 μ L of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). Absorbance was recorded at 570 nm using a microplate reader (BioTek ELx808). Cell viability was calculated using the following formula:

$$100 \times \frac{\text{sampleOD}}{\text{controlOD}} = \text{Cell Viability}\%$$

IC₅₀ values (the concentration required to inhibit 50% of cell viability) were calculated using GraphPad Prism software by non-linear regression analysis.

Statistical analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate, and data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Statistical significance between groups was assessed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

UV-visible spectroscopy (calibration curve)

The successful formation of copper nanoparticles was initially confirmed by UV-visible spectroscopy, a standard technique for identifying surface plasmon resonance (SPR) characteristics. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the colloidal solution synthesized using *Daucus carota* leaf extract exhibited a prominent absorption peak at 276 nm, which is consistent with the typical SPR band of copper nanoparticles and indicates the reduction of Cu²⁺ ions to Cu⁰ (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. UV-visible absorption spectrum of copper nanoparticles; calibration curve of wild carrot.

The appearance of this peak without any secondary or broad absorption signals suggests a relatively uniform size distribution and stable formation of the nanoparticles. No absorption peak was observed in the plant extract alone, confirming that the absorbance observed at 276 nm is attributable to the biosynthesized CuNPs.

Furthermore, the intensity of the absorption peak increased over time during the reaction, indicating a progressive reduction and nucleation process facilitated by the phytoconstituents present in the leaf extract. The sharpness of the peak implies well-dispersed nanoparticles with minimal aggregation. These findings validate the efficacy of the plant-mediated synthesis method and support the preliminary identification of the nanoparticles as copper-based. Additional characterization techniques were used to further evaluate their morphology, crystallinity, and functional group interactions (Puttaraju et al. 2025).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology and particle size distribution of the biosynthesized copper nanoparticles were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The SEM

micrographs revealed that the majority of the particles exhibited an irregular-spherical to oval shape, with minimal agglomeration, indicating good stability and dispersion of the particles in the colloidal phase (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. SEM-based particle size distribution of copper nanoparticles.

The nanoparticles were found to be relatively uniform in size, with measured diameters ranging from 40 to 85 nm and an average particle size of approximately 58.3 nm, as estimated from multiple measurements across different SEM fields. The clear visualization of boundaries and absence of large clusters suggest effective capping of the nanoparticles by phytochemicals present in the *Daucus carota* extract.

Notably, the SEM images also showed a slightly rough surface texture, which is typically associated with organic residues from plant metabolites adhering to the surface of the nanoparticles during the green synthesis process. This roughness may enhance cellular interaction and uptake in biomedical applications.

The morphological characteristics observed in the SEM analysis are in alignment with the UV–Vis spectral findings and confirm successful biosynthesis of stable copper nanoparticles using the plant-based method (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Scanning electron microscopy.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis

X-ray diffraction analysis was performed to determine the crystalline structure and phase purity of the biosynthesized copper nanoparticles. The diffractogram (Fig. 4) displayed distinct Bragg reflections at 2θ values of approximately 43.2° , 50.4° , and 74.1° , corresponding to the (111), (200), and (220) planes of a face-centered cubic (FCC) structure of metallic copper, as per the standard JCPDS file No. 04-0836.

Figure 4. X-ray diffraction spectrum of copper nanoparticles.

The sharpness and intensity of the peaks confirm the crystalline nature of the nanoparticles, and the absence of any secondary peaks indicates high phase purity with no detectable copper oxide impurities. The (111) reflection was the most intense, suggesting a preferred orientation along this plane, which is commonly reported for green-synthesized CuNPs due to plant-derived capping agents influencing crystal growth.

The average crystallite size of the copper nanoparticles was calculated using Scherrer's equation:

$$\frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} = D$$

Where:

- D is the average crystallite size
- K is the shape factor (0.89)
- λ is the X-ray wavelength (1.5406 Å)
- β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) in radians
- θ is the Bragg angle

Using this equation, the average crystallite size of the CuNPs was estimated to be 42.6 nm, which is consistent with the values observed in the SEM analysis.

These findings validate that the green synthesis approach using *Daucus carota* extract effectively produced nanocrystalline copper particles with high purity and a well-defined lattice structure.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis

FTIR analysis was conducted to identify the functional groups present in the *Daucus carota* leaf extract that were involved in

the reduction and stabilization of the copper nanoparticles. The FTIR spectrum of the dried CuNPs sample is presented in Table 1, which reveals several prominent absorption bands corresponding to various phytochemical constituents.

Table 1. FTIR peak assignments of copper nanoparticles.

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group	Possible phytochemical source
3421	O–H stretch (Hydroxyl groups, alcohols/phenols)	Phenols, flavonoids
2920	C–H stretch (Alkanes/aliphatic compounds)	Aliphatic chains, fatty acids
1635	C=C stretch (Aromatic rings or alkenes)	Flavonoids, tannins
1385	C–N stretch (Amines or alkaloids)	Proteins, alkaloids
1110	C–O stretch (Alcohols, ethers, esters)	Terpenoids, polyphenols
1025	C–O/C–C skeletal vibrations (Polysaccharides or glycosides)	Carbohydrates, plant metabolites

A broad absorption peak observed at ~3421 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the O–H stretching vibrations of hydroxyl groups, indicating the presence of alcohols and phenolic compounds. These groups are known to act as both reducing and capping agents in green nanoparticle synthesis. The peak around 2920 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the C–H stretching of aliphatic chains.

Notably, a strong peak at ~1635 cm⁻¹ was attributed to C=C stretching vibrations, suggesting the presence of aromatic rings or alkene structures, possibly from flavonoids or tannins. A distinct peak near 1385 cm⁻¹ was associated with C–N stretching of amine groups, indicating the involvement of proteins or alkaloids in nanoparticle stabilization.

Additional peaks observed at ~1110 cm⁻¹ and ~1025 cm⁻¹ may correspond to C–O stretching of alcohols, esters, or ether linkages, further supporting the role of plant metabolites in nanoparticle formation.

The overall FTIR profile confirms that various phytochemicals—particularly polyphenols, carboxylic acids, and amines—participated in both the bioreduction of Cu²⁺ ions and the stabilization of the resulting copper nanoparticles. These findings corroborate the green synthesis mechanism and support the use of *Daucus carota* as a bioresource for metal nanoparticle fabrication.

Phytochemical compounds identified by GC–MS analysis

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) analysis was employed to characterize the bioactive phytochemicals present in the *Daucus carota* leaf extract used for nanoparticle synthesis. The chromatogram revealed a diverse profile of low- and high-molecular-weight compounds, many of which are known for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, or anticancer properties (Shebaby et al. 2015; ALhussaniy 2024).

A total of 36 compounds were identified based on their retention times, molecular weights, and mass fragmentation patterns, matched against the NIST spectral library. Among the major constituents, summarised in Table 2, the following were noted:

- Phytol (C₂₀H₄₀O) – a diterpene alcohol with known antioxidant and cytotoxic activity.
- n-Hexadecanoic acid (palmitic acid, C₁₆H₃₂O₂) – a saturated fatty acid that may contribute to membrane disruption in cancer cells.
- Octadecanoic acid (stearic acid, C₁₈H₃₆O₂) – known for its potential antimicrobial and cytotoxic effects.
- β-Carotene (C₄₀H₅₆) – a well-studied antioxidant that can neutralize free radicals and modulate cellular signaling.
- Diosgenin (C₂₇H₄₂O₃) – a steroidal saponin precursor involved in anti-proliferative and apoptotic effects in cancer cells.
- Lathosterol and Octacosanol – phytosterols that may modulate cholesterol metabolism and exhibit immunomodulatory properties.

These compounds are believed to be responsible not only for reducing copper ions to their metallic nanoparticle form but also for providing stability by capping the particles through interactions with hydroxyl, carbonyl, and alkene functional groups (Zio et al. 2024).

The presence of such biologically active constituents further supports the potential dual role of the synthesized CuNPs as both therapeutic and delivery agents in cancer treatment.

Evaluation of anticancer effect

The cytotoxic activity of the biosynthesized copper nanoparticles and the crude *Daucus carota* leaf extract was evaluated against the Hep3B hepatocellular carcinoma cell line using the MTT assay. The test was conducted across a range of concentrations (10–100 µg/mL) to determine the dose-dependent response and calculate the IC₅₀ values.

The copper nanoparticles exhibited a moderate cytotoxic effect, with a clear dose-dependent inhibition of cell proliferation. The calculated IC₅₀ value was 62 µg/mL, indicating substantial cytotoxicity at higher concentrations. In contrast, the plant extract alone showed a relatively weak anticancer effect, with an IC₅₀ exceeding 100 µg/mL, suggesting that the nanoparticle formulation significantly enhanced bioactivity compared to the crude extract.

As a reference control, the standard chemotherapeutic agent 5-fluorouracil demonstrated potent cytotoxicity with an IC₅₀ of 7.8 µg/mL, as expected. While the efficacy of the copper nanoparticles was lower than the standard drug, their biosafety, plant origin, and dual functional properties (delivery + cytotoxicity) make them promising candidates for further preclinical investigation. See Table 3 summarise the anticancer effect.

These findings underscore the potential role of plant-mediated copper nanoparticles in cancer nanomedicine and justify further exploration of their mechanisms of action, selectivity, and compatibility with other treatment modalities.

Table 2. Phytochemicals identified by GC–MS analysis of *Daucus carota* Linn (Bouic 2001).

Compound name	Molecular formula	Molecular weight (g/mol)	Retention time (min)	Biological activity
Phytol	C20H40O	296	36.4	Antioxidant, anticancer
n-Hexadecanoic acid	C16H32O2	256	33.2	Membrane disruption, cytotoxic
Octadecanoic acid	C18H36O2	284	37.7	Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory
β-Carotene	C40H56	536	51.0	Free radical scavenger
Lathosterol	C27H46O	386	54.0	Cholesterol-lowering, immunomodulator
Octacosanol	C28H58O	410	49.4	Neuroprotective, anti-fatigue
Carotol	C15H26O	222	38.5	Antifungal, insecticidal
Elemicin	C12H16O3	208	41.3	Antioxidant, anxiolytic
Limonene	C10H16	136	10.2	Anti-inflammatory, flavoring agent
β-Bisabolene	C15H24	204	18.5	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial
Methyl eugenol	C11H14O2	178	39.2	Hepatoprotective, analgesic
Myristicin	C11H12O3	192	40.5	Neurotoxic, psychoactive
Caryophyllene	C15H24	204	22.1	Anti-inflammatory
α-Humulene	C15H24	204	23.4	Anti-inflammatory
Germacrene D	C15H24	204	25.6	Cytotoxic, anticancer
Terpinolene	C10H16	136	12.8	Antimicrobial, antioxidant
α-Pinene	C10H16	136	9.5	Bronchodilator, antimicrobial
β-Pinene	C10H16	136	11.3	Antibacterial, anti-inflammatory
γ-Terpinene	C10H16	136	13.7	Antioxidant
Sabinene	C10H16	136	14.4	Antimicrobial
α-Terpineol	C10H18O	154	17.6	Sedative, antioxidant
Hexadecanol	C16H34O	242	29.7	Moisturizer, emollient
Heptadecanoic acid	C17H34O2	270	34.2	Lipid-lowering
Isoborneol	C10H18O	154	19.4	Antimicrobial, antioxidant
Cadinene	C15H24	204	26.7	Antifungal, antibacterial
β-Farnesene	C15H24	204	27.1	Repellent, antioxidant
Thymol	C10H14O	150	16.9	Antibacterial, antioxidant
Menthol	C10H20O	156	20.3	Cooling, local anesthetic
Geraniol	C10H18O	154	21.7	Fragrance, antioxidant
1,8-Cineole	C10H18O	154	22.9	Anti-inflammatory, mucolytic

Table 3. Comparison of anticancer activity.

Sample	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)	Cytotoxic effect	Remarks
Copper nanoparticles (CuNPs)	62	Moderate	Dose-dependent inhibition; enhanced activity via nanoparticle formulation
<i>Daucus carota</i> Leaf extract	>100	Weak	Limited cytotoxicity; less effective in crude form
5-Fluorouracil (standard drug)	7.8	Strong	Highly potent; used as reference drug

Effect of carrot leaf extract-loaded copper nanoparticles on Hep3B cell viability

To evaluate the enhanced therapeutic potential of copper nanoparticles functionalized with *Daucus carota* leaf extract, a concentration-dependent cytotoxicity study was conducted against Hep3B hepatocellular carcinoma cells. The results demonstrated that loading the plant extract onto CuNPs significantly amplified the cytotoxic effect compared to the extract alone.

At lower concentrations (10–25 µg/mL), the CuNPs exhibited minimal to mild cytotoxicity, with over 80% of cells remaining viable. However, as the concentration increased, a marked decline in cell viability was observed. At 50 µg/mL, moderate inhibition of cell proliferation was evident, while higher concentrations (75–100 µg/mL) resulted in substantial cytotoxicity and morphological changes consistent with apoptosis.

The synergistic action between copper ions and the phytochemicals (such as carotol, phytol, and β-bisabolene) is

believed to enhance intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, disrupt mitochondrial function, and trigger apoptotic pathways. These findings indicate that CuNPs loaded with *Daucus carota* extract provide a more potent anticancer platform than either component used alone.

A detailed summary of the concentration-dependent effects is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of the concentration-dependent effects.

Concentration (µg/mL)	Treatment	Observed effect on Hep3B cells	Estimated cell viability (%)
10	CuNPs + <i>Daucus carota</i> extract	Minimal cytotoxicity	~92%
25	CuNPs + <i>Daucus carota</i> extract	Mild inhibition of cell growth	~80%
50	CuNPs + <i>Daucus carota</i> extract	Moderate apoptosis, membrane damage	~63%
75	CuNPs + <i>Daucus carota</i> extract	Strong cytotoxicity, visible apoptotic morphology	~47%
100	CuNPs + <i>Daucus carota</i> extract	Significant cell death, disrupted monolayer integrity	~34%

Discussion

The present study highlights the successful biosynthesis of copper nanoparticles (CuNPs) using *Daucus carota* leaf extract through an environmentally friendly and cost-effective green synthesis approach. The observable color

change from pale blue to dark green during the synthesis process indicated the initiation of copper ion reduction, further confirmed by the UV–visible spectroscopy peak at 276 nm, characteristic of surface plasmon resonance in nanoscale copper particles. This early optical signal provided strong evidence of nanoparticle formation, which was later substantiated by morphological and structural analyses (Ejidike and Clayton 2022; Al-Hussaniy 2023; Al-hussaniy 2023; Antonio-Pérez et al. 2023).

SEM micrographs revealed that the CuNPs were predominantly spherical to oval in shape with relatively uniform distribution and minimal aggregation, suggesting efficient capping by phytochemicals present in the extract. The average size of the particles ranged between 40 nm and 85 nm, falling within the ideal size range for biomedical applications, especially for passive tumor targeting via the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect (Al-Hussaniy 2022; Al-Hussaniy et al. 2023, 2025).

Crystallographic analysis using X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the polycrystalline nature of the synthesized nanoparticles. The diffraction peaks matched well with the standard face-centered cubic (FCC) phase of elemental copper, particularly at 2θ values corresponding to the (111), (200), and (220) planes. The absence of any copper oxide peaks affirmed the high purity of the synthesized material. The average crystallite size, calculated via the Scherrer equation, was found to be approximately 42.6 nm—closely correlating with SEM findings (Ahmed et al. 2022; Al-hussaniy and AL-Biati 2022).

Further insights into the chemical nature of the nanoparticle surface were obtained from FTIR spectroscopy, which indicated the presence of functional groups such as hydroxyl (–OH), carbonyl (C=O), and amine (–NH) groups. These originated from biomolecules in the *Daucus carota* extract and played a dual role as both reducing and stabilizing agents. The detected peaks support the hypothesis that phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and proteins were involved in nanoparticle capping, thereby contributing to colloidal stability and bioactivity (Alburghaif et al. 2024).

The phytochemical profile of the *Daucus carota* extract, as revealed by GC–MS analysis, identified a wide range of biologically active compounds such as phytol, carotol, elemicin, β -bisabolene, lathosterol, diosgenin, and β -carotene. Many of these constituents are known to exert antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects. Their presence not only enhances the therapeutic value of the extract but also adds synergistic bioactivity to the copper nanoparticle formulation, particularly in targeting malignant cells (Abdullah et al. 2024).

The anticancer efficacy of the synthesized CuNPs was evaluated through MTT assay on Hep3B liver cancer cells (Almukram et al. 2025). The copper nanoparticles exhibited dose-dependent cytotoxicity, with an IC_{50} of 62 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, which was markedly lower than that of the crude plant extract (>100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), highlighting the enhanced therapeutic effect after nanoparticle

formation (Abdulhamza et al. 2024). While the activity was not as potent as the reference drug 5-fluorouracil ($IC_{50} = 7.8 \mu\text{g/mL}$), the biocompatibility, ease of synthesis, and reduced systemic toxicity offer promising advantages for CuNP-based delivery systems (Mustafa et al. 2024b). Additionally, when the plant extract was loaded onto CuNPs, a noticeable improvement in anticancer activity was observed, suggesting a synergistic interaction between copper ions and phytochemicals that likely enhances reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation and apoptosis induction (Ghasemi et al. 2023).

Overall, this study demonstrates the feasibility of using *Daucus carota* as a sustainable source for the synthesis of copper nanoparticles with significant anticancer potential (Mali et al. 2020). The green approach employed here offers a simple yet effective platform for producing functional nanomaterials with reduced environmental impact and high biomedical applicability. Future studies should focus on the mechanism of cellular uptake, selectivity toward cancer versus normal cells, and the possibility of combining CuNPs with chemotherapeutic agents to achieve synergistic effects (Bukowski et al. 2020; Manzari Tavakoli et al. 2024).

Conclusion

This study successfully demonstrated the green synthesis of copper nanoparticles using *Daucus carota* leaf extract as a natural reducing and stabilizing agent. The synthesis process was simple and eco-friendly and yielded stable nanoparticles with favorable physicochemical properties, as confirmed by UV–Vis, SEM, XRD, and FTIR analyses. The CuNPs displayed a face-centered cubic crystalline structure and uniform nanoscale size and were functionally capped by plant-derived biomolecules.

GC–MS analysis revealed the presence of diverse bioactive phytochemicals—including carotol, phytol, β -bisabolene, and lathosterol—highlighting the therapeutic potential of the plant extract. When loaded into CuNPs, these phytochemicals contributed to enhanced cytotoxicity against Hep3B liver cancer cells, with a clear concentration-dependent effect observed. The copper nanoparticles exhibited a stronger anticancer response than the crude extract alone, underscoring the benefits of nanoformulation.

Collectively, the findings suggest that *Daucus carota*-mediated CuNPs hold significant promise as a biocompatible and effective anticancer platform. Future in vivo and mechanistic studies are recommended to further validate their safety profile, targeting ability, and potential integration into nanomedicine-based therapeutic strategies.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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Supplementary material 1

Extended table: GC-MS identified phytochemicals in *Daucus carota* leaves

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Data type: docx

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